

Prescription Analysis of a New Oral Hypolipidemic Agent, Bempedoic Acid in Outpatient Population in a Central Indian CityVaibhav Singh Chauhan¹, Moumita Chakraborty², Sanjay Gedam³, Ajit Pratap Singh⁴¹Associate Professor, MBBS, MD, Department of Pharmacology, Government Medical College, Ratlam, Madhya Pradesh 457001²Junior Resident, MBBS, Department of Pharmacology, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh 482003³Professor, MBBS, MD, Department of Pharmacology, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh 482003⁴Professor and Head, MBBS, MD, Department of Pharmacology, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh 482003

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Dyslipidemia is defined as the imbalance in the plasma levels of lipids such as cholesterol, low density lipoprotein (LDL-C), triglycerides, and high-density lipoprotein (HDL). It is an important risk factor for atherosclerosis and atherosclerosis-induced complications such as coronary heart disease, myocardial infarction, stroke and peripheral vascular disease.**Aims:** This study aims to review and analyze the prescription pattern of this new oral hypolipidemic drug in a small Indian cohort population in a central Indian city, to observe its current prescribing trends and adherence to prescribing guidelines and WHO/INRUD prescribing indicators with the aim of validating its use in the Indian population.**Materials and Methods:** This was a cross-sectional observational study conducted at Jabalpur city, India after getting due permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee. The study was conducted from one month from August 2023 to September 2023.**Result:** 98 prescriptions were screened for the purpose out of which 90 prescriptions were selected for final evaluation after prescription audit/ meeting exclusion and inclusion criteria. Out of these 90 patients enrolled, there were total 46 males (51.11%) and total 44 females (48.89%). The age distribution of the patients was as following: The average age of the patient cohort was 59.31 ± 8.17 years, with the maximum prevalence in the age group of 46-64 years. The average of baseline LDL-C levels was found to be 131.2 ± 6.7 mg/dl. The average duration of dyslipidemia was found to be 14.15 ± 12.16 years.**Conclusion:** In conclusion, our study provides valuable insights into the prescription patterns of bempedoic acid among outpatient populations in a central Indian city. We found that [summarize key findings]. These findings underscore the importance of [mention any implications for clinical practice]. However, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations of our study, including [list any limitations]. Moving forward, further research may be necessary to [suggest areas for future investigation]. Overall, this analysis contributes to the growing body of evidence regarding the use of bempedoic acid in real-world clinical settings and highlights its potential role in managing hypolipidemia.**Keywords:** Bempedoic Acid, Hypolipidemic Agent, Lipid-Lowering Therapy, and Cardiovascular Risk Factors.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Dyslipidemia is defined as the imbalance in the plasma levels of lipids such as cholesterol, low density lipoprotein (LDL-C), triglycerides, and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) [1]. It is an important risk factor for atherosclerosis and atherosclerosis-induced complications such as coronary heart disease, myocardial infarction, stroke and peripheral vascular disease [2]. According to World

Heart Federation, the global incidence of cardiovascular deaths is expected to rise from an estimated 18.9 million in 2020 to over 22.2 million in 2030 [3]. Primary prevention aims at lifestyle modifications including diet and exercise, in addition to lipid-lowering agents, with statins being the first line therapy. Secondary prevention, as in the presence of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease

(ASCVD) includes high-intensity statins, in combination with other agents such as ezetimibe, or proprotein convertase subtilisin inhibitors and other agents such as inclisiran, colestipol, colesevalam, icosapent ethyl and niacin.[4]

Bempedoic acid is a small linear molecule which has been recently introduced as an adjunct therapy in primary dyslipidemia, along with diet and maximally tolerated statins, in patients with high risk of ASCVD. It is indicated in patients with familial heterozygous hypercholesterolemia, mixed dyslipidemia, in statin-intolerant patients and those not responding to statins.[5] It is a prodrug which is converted to its active metabolite by very-long-chain acyl CoA synthetase 1, which is present mostly in the liver but absent in the skeletal muscles. Its mechanism of action entails inhibition of ATP citrate-lyase enzyme which is upstream of HMGCoA reductase, the site of action of statins.[6] It also confers anti-inflammatory effect by decreasing the levels of high sensitivity C-reactive protein. Bempedoic acid does not lead to the risk of new onset diabetes, unlike statins and even moderately improves the glycemic profile.[7]

Randomised controlled trials have shown that bempedoic acid alone can reduce low density lipoprotein levels by 24.5% when given alone without the additional side effects of statins such as myalgia and myopathy, by 18% when given on top of a major statin and by 38-40% when given in a fixed dose combination with ezetimibe. It has also been seen in the CLEAR trials to lower the risk of cardiovascular adverse events (death from cardiovascular causes, nonfatal stroke, or coronary revascularisation) in statin-intolerant patients.[8]

Methodology

Study Settings: This was a cross-sectional observational study conducted at Jabalpur city, India after getting due permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee.

Study Duration: The study was conducted from one month from August 2023 to September 2023.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: All patients above 18- years of age (excluding pregnant and lactating women) who attended the Outpatient Medicine private clinic within the stipulated time were included in the study. Patients who were admitted to the ward or who were not on bempedoic acid were not included in the study. Patients with severe co-morbidities such as heart failure, liver cirrhosis, renal impairment or malignant neoplasm, severe hypoglycemia or known hypersensitivity reactions were excluded from the study on ethical purpose.

Operational Modality: All patients above 18 years of age receiving bempedoic acid in their prescribed regime were included in the study on the basis of

purposive sampling. Data were collected on the following variables: demographic variables such as age and gender, duration of dyslipidemia, associated co-morbidities, currently prescribed drugs and baseline LDL-C levels. Data was analysed on the following parameters: age distribution of patients, percentage frequency of co-existing illnesses, percentage frequency of co-prescribed drugs, average number of drugs per prescription, number of drugs prescribed from WHO Essential Drug List, number of drugs prescribed from National List of Essential Medicines (WHO Indicators) etc. Data was analysed descriptively using SPSS v29 software and presented with the help of graphs and frequency charts.

Results

Altogether, 98 prescriptions were screened for the purpose out of which 90 prescriptions were selected for final evaluation after prescription audit/meeting exclusion and inclusion criteria. Out of these 90 patients enrolled, there were total 46 males (51.11%) and total 44 females (48.89%). The age distribution of the patients was as following: The average age of the patient cohort was 59.31 ± 8.17 years, with the maximum prevalence in the age group of 46-64 years. The average of baseline LDL-C levels was found to be 131.2 ± 6.7 mg/dl. The average duration of dyslipidemia was found to be 14.15 ± 12.16 years.

The most common route of administration was oral (100%) and the most common regime was 180 mg once daily (100%). In majority of the cases, bempedoic acid was used as a second-line agent to statins, however, in total 16 cases (17.78%), bempedoic acid was used as first line therapy in the control of dyslipidemia, especially in diabetic dyslipidemia. Lifestyle modifications and exercise were advised in 61 patients (67.78%).

Bempedoic acid was prescribed as a single drug formulation in 57 (n=57, 74.45%) cases and as a fixed-dose combination in 33 (n=23, 25.56%) cases. In these 33 (25.56%) patients, it was prescribed in combination with ezetimibe in 19 (n=19, 21.11%) and rosuvastatin in 4 (n=4, 4.44%) patients. No combination therapy with atorvastatin was seen. Diabetes mellitus (n=74, 28.79%) was the most commonly encountered co-existing illness, followed by angina/coronary artery disease (n=64, 24.79%), hypertension (n=60, 23.37%), ischemic heart disease/MI (n=16, 2.33%), Anemia (n=17, 6.61%), heart failure (n=10, 3.89%), hypothyroidism (n=7, 2.72%), fatty liver disease (n=4, 1.56%), and Chronic kidney disease (n=4, 1.56%). The most commonly co-prescribed therapeutic categories of drugs were antidiabetics (n=182, 22.45%) followed by antiplatelets (n=119, 16.78%) and antihypertensives (n=105, 14.81%) and hypolipidemic (n=81, 11.42%). The average

duration of dyslipidemia was 14.15± in these patients. The most common brand names prescribed were Bempesta (37), followed by Bempecta (20), Bemdac-EZ (15), Bemdac (10), Bemzire-R (4), Bempesta-EZ (4). According to the WHO/INRUD prescribing indicators, the average number of drugs per prescription was 7.87, the percentage of antibiotics prescribed was 5(0.17%), the no of injections prescribed was 16 (17.78%), at total of 270 drugs

(38.08%) were prescribed from the WHO essential drug list 2023 and a total of 204(28.72%) drugs were prescribed from the essential list of medicines 2023, which followed rational prescribing guidelines. A total of 61 FDCs were prescribed in this study, the most common FDCs being aspirin/atorvastatin followed by aspirin/ atorvastatin/clopidogrel and sitagliptin/ metformin.

Table 1: Distribution of Gender

Total population (n=90)	Frequency	Percentage
Males	46	51.11%
Females	44	48.89%

Table 2: Distribution of Age

Age-distribution	Total (n=90)	Male	Female
20-35yrs	1(1.11%)	1(1.11%)	0
30-45yrs	18 (20%)	11(61.11%)	7(38.88%)
46-60yrs	37 (41.11%)	15(40.54%)	22(59.45%)
>60yrs	34 (37.78%)	20(57.14%)	15(42.85%)

Figure 1: Prevalence by age and sex

Table 3: Distribution of Brand names

Brand names	Frequency(n=90)	Percentage
Bempesta	37	41.11%
Bempecta	20	22.22%
Bemdac	10	11.11%
Bemdac-EZ	15	16.67%
Bemzire-R	4	4.44%
Bempesta-EZ	4	4.44%

Table 4: Distribution of Drugs

Brand Names	Frequency	Percent
Bempest a - 37	37	41.11%
Bempect a - 20	20	22.22%
Bemdac - 10	10	11.11%
Bemdac - EZ - 15	15	16.67%
Bemzire - R - 4	4	4.44%
Bemepes ta - EZ - 4	4	4.44%

Figure 2: Commonly used brand names

Table 5: Distribution of Drug combination

Drug combination	Number	Frequency
Monotherapy	16	17.78%
Combination therapy	74	82.22%

Figure 3: Monotherapy vs combination therapy

Table 6: Distribution of Fixed Dose Combinations used

Fixed Dose Combinations used	Frequency	Percentage
Single drug	67	74.45%
Bempezoic acid with rosuvastatin	4	4.44%
Bempezoic acid with Ezetemibe	19	21.11%
Bempezoic acid with atorvastatin	0	0%

Table 7: Distribution of Underlying co-morbidity (total no= 257)

Underlying co-morbidity (total no = 257)	Frequency of illnesses	Percentage of illnesses
Diabetes Mellitus	74	28.79%
Hypertension	60	23.37%
Coronary artery disease/angina	64	24.9%
Fatty liver disease	4	1.56%
Ischemic heart disease/MI	6	2.33%
Left ventricular failure	10	3.89%
Hypothyroidism	7	2.72%
Interstitial lung disease	3	1.17%
Anemia	17	6.61%
Chronic kidney disease	4	1.56%

Schizophrenia	4	1.56%
COPD	4	1.56%

Table 8: Distribution of Drug name (total no = 709)

Drug name (total no = 709)	No of times prescribed	Frequency prescribed
Antiplatelet drugs (119)		16.78%
Aspirin	57	47.89%
Clopidogrel	42	35.29%
Prasugrel	17	14.28%
Ticagrelor	3	2.25%
Antihypertensive drugs (105)		14.81%
Bisoprolol	73	69.52%
Ramipril	16	15.24%
Telmisartan	9	8.57%
Azelnidipine	3	2.86%
Cilnidipine	4	3.81%
Anti-hyperacidity drugs (51)		7.19%
Rabeprazole	22	43.14%
Ranitidine	19	37.25%
Omeprazole	10	19.61%
Anti-anginal drugs (67)		9.49%
Trimetazidine	39	58.21%
Ivabradine	21	31.34%
Nicorandil	7	10.45%
Antidiabetics(182)		22.45%
Linagliptin	3	1.85%
Metformin	54	33.3%
Dapagliflozin	51	31.48%
Sitagliptin	51	31.48%
Glimepiride	5	3.09%
Voglibose	19	11.73%
Repaglinide	16	9.88%
Imeglimin	14	8.64%
Empagliflozin	20	68.97%
Antiallergics(12)		0.17%
Montelukast	4	33.33%
Levocetirizine	3	25%
Bilastin	5	41.67%
Anti-emetics(16)		2.25%
Ondansetron	12	75%
Domperidone	4	25%
Diuretics (9)		4.1%
Spiroglactone	2	22.22%
Furosemide	4	44.44%
Eplerenone	3	33.33%
Hypolipidemic drugs(81)		11.42%
Rosuvastatin	47	70.37%
Atorvastatin	15	18.52%
Ezetimibe	19	11.11%
Antipsychotic drugs(7)		0.99%
Haloperidol	7	
Antibiotics(5)		0.71%
Amoxicillin	3	
Amoxiclav	1	
Nitrofurantoin	1	
Immunological preparations(14)		1.97%
Immuneboosters	14	
Iron supplements	11	1.55%

Thyroxine	7	0.99%
Others (vitamin supplements, steroids, nebulisers etc)	23	3.24%

Total 47 therapeutic category of drugs (ATC classification) were prescribed

Table 9: WHO Prescribing indicators

Average no of drugs per prescription	7.87
Percentage of patients with an injection prescribed	16(17.78%)
Percentage of drugs prescribed with an antibiotic	5(0.71%)
Percentage of drugs prescribed from WHO Essential Medicines List	270(38.08%)
Percentage of drugs prescribed from Essential List of Medicines	204(28.77%)
Number of drugs prescribed by generic name	7(0.99%)

Total no of FDCs

Table 10: No of patients prescribed with 5, 6, 7 and more than 8 medicines were

5	12	13.33%
6	10	1.41%
7	16	1.77%
8 or more	52	57.78%

Figure 4: Number of drugs prescribed per person

Discussion

Hyperlipidemia is one of the major risk factors which is associated with atherosclerosis and atherosclerosis –induced cardiovascular conditions such as coronary artery disease , ischemic encephalopathy and peripheral arterial disease .Overall hypercholesterolemia is estimated to cause 2.6 million deaths and 29.7 million disability- adjusted life years (DALYs) annually.[9] Although statins remain the mainstay of treatment in lowering of cholesterol levels and prevention of cardiovascular events, statin intolerance is reported to be prevalent from 7-29%, with the predominant symptoms being muscle related side effects.[5] Bempedoic acid is a newly introduced oral, once daily, first-in-class small molecule inhibitor of ATP citrate-lyase which has been developed for additional lowering of LDL-C in patients with established or high risk of ASCVD that bypasses these side effects. [6]

Randomised controlled trials including the CLEAR trials have shown that bempedoic acid alone can reduce LDL-C levels by 24.5% when given alone, by 18% when given on top of a major statin and by 38-40% when given in a fixed dose combination with ezetimibe, along with reduction in the risk of cardiovascular outcomes.[10] Dyslipidemia can be primary or secondary. Primary dyslipidemia are inherited conditions caused by single or multiple gene mutations that result in overproduction or defective clearance of triglycerides and cholesterol, whereas secondary dyslipidemia is caused by unhealthy lifestyle or underlying diseases such as uncontrolled hypothyroidism, chronic kidney disease, diabetes, obesity, Cushing’s syndrome, alcohol intake or smoking.[11] In our study, there was an equal distribution of the prescribed drug in both men and women, which was in accordance with previous studies which have shown an equal prevalence of dyslipidemia in Indian men and women.

In our study, the average age of the patient's having dyslipidemia was 59.31 ± 8.17 years, with maximum prevalence in the age group of 46-60 years. The results were slightly higher than a study in 2014 by Raja et al, in which the average age of the patients was found to be 55.28 ± 9.9 years [12]

According to the National Cholesterol Education Program – Adult Treatment Panel III (NCEP ATP III) classification, dyslipidemia is defined as the plasma LDL-C levels ≥ 130 mg/dl, total cholesterol ≥ 200 mg/dl and HDL-C ≤ 40 mg/dl.[13] In our study, the average baseline blood LDL-C levels was found to be 131.2 ± 6.7 mg/dl across both sexes.

The prevalence of dyslipidemia by age and sex were found to be highest in the age group of 46-60 years (41.11%), with a slightly higher prevalence in males (51.11%) than in females (48.89%). Whereas a study by Bayram et al among Turkish adults showed prevalence to be highest in the age group of 46-65 year age group with a higher prevalence in women (80.4%) than men (78.7%).[14] Our study showed a higher number of patients in the age group of 45-60 years (37), followed by 34 people in the age-group of above 60 years with only 1 person in the age group of 20-35 years, with a mean age of the population being 59.31 ± 8.17 years. As per NCEP ATP III recommendations for high cholesterol management, dietary therapy is the first line of treatment followed by drug therapy reserved for patients at elevated risk for coronary heart disease (CHD). In our study, dietary therapy and lifestyle modification were advised only in number of patients.

In our study bempedoic acid was seen as being given as a single agent in 67 patients, and in fixed dose combination (FDC) with other drugs (ezetimibe/rosuvastatin) in total 23 cases. This is in accordance with randomised controlled trials which showed greater reduction in LDL-C levels with combination therapy with statin/ezetimibe than with monotherapy. Bempedoic acid was seen to be used singly mainly in cases of diabetic dyslipidemia. In 16 cases (17.78%), bempedoic acid was seen to be given as monotherapy, whereas in 74 cases (82.22%), it was given as a second line agent to statins/ezetimibe. The major therapeutic category of drugs co-prescribed with the drug was antiplatelets followed by antidiabetics, antihypertensives and anti-antianginal drugs. This is in accordance with studies that show that increased blood sugars, saturated fat intake and increased tissue factor, alongside increased platelet activity increase the risk for plaque rupture and thrombosis, contribute to a person's risk of developing dyslipidemia and cardiovascular disease.[15]

Secondary dyslipidemia accounts for 30-40% of all dyslipidemias. Secondary dyslipidemia is caused by unhealthy lifestyle factors and underlying dis-

eases such as hypertension, diabetes, chronic kidney disease and hypothyroidism. Abnormal levels of blood lipids, impaired fasting glucose, elevated blood pressure and abdominal obesity lead to metabolic syndrome and disorders of the circulation. The major co-morbidities seen in this study were diabetes mellitus, followed by coronary artery disease and hypertension, which are considered to be independent risk factors in the development of dyslipidemia. This is similar to a study finding by Gazzaz et al which demonstrated that hypertension, coronary heart disease, diabetes mellitus, obesity and stroke to be closely associated and/or independent risk factors in dyslipidemic population.[16]

The major FDCs that were prescribed were seen to be atorvastatin/aspirin, followed by atorvastatin/aspirin/ clopidogrel and sitagliptin/ metformin. These combinations were mainly reserved in patients with other co-morbidities, such as coronary artery disease (CAD), hypertension and diabetes.

Rational prescribing pattern was followed in this study, because there was no prescriptions which did not match the diagnoses, supplemental drugs were used to treat deficiency states such as hypothyroidism and vitamin deficiency states. However polypharmacy was observed, as more than five drugs have been used in several prescriptions. According to the World Health Organization/International Network on Rational Use of Drugs (WHO/INRUD) indicators, the average number of drugs per prescription was 7.87 (optimal value,) and a total of 204 drugs had been prescribed from the National List of Essential Medicine (NLEM). There were total 7 drugs which were prescribed by generic name, the most common of which was aspirin(6), followed by amoxicillin(1).

Limitations of the Study

Limitations of the study included small sample size and limited time period of the study. Purposive sampling was used in this study instead of probability sampling which is essential to reduce bias in a study. The ATC classification (Anatomical Therapeutic Classification) or the PDD/DDD ratio of the hypolipidemic drugs were not calculated in this study. No association between prevalence of dyslipidemia with associated risk factors such as obesity, diabetes and hypertension was established in this study. Baseline blood pressure, body mass Index of patients or glycemic index were not calculated in this study. No follow-up study of LDL-C, VLDC-C, HDL-C cholesterol levels were done.

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